

Legal Basis of Social Protection of Women and Gender Equality

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Abstract

This article discusses the fact that at a new stage in the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, work on the social protection of women has reached a new level and its legal framework has been created. This is evidenced by the analysis of the active participation of women in the elections in the country in 2019 and the opportunities and conditions created for them, as well as the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 2, 2019 No. 562 "On guarantees of equal rights and opportunities for women and men". Law No. 561 "On the Protection of Women from Oppression and Violence", Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 2, 2018 No. 5325 "On measures to radically improve activities in the field of supporting women and strengthening the institution of the family", No. PQ-3827 dated July 2, 2018 "On measures to improve the system of social rehabilitation and adaptation, as well as the prevention of domestic violence", March 7, 2019 "On further strengthening the guarantees of women's labor rights and supporting entrepreneurship No. PQ-4235" On measures to strengthen ", the decision is made as legal basis.

IJOBAS

Accepted 4 July 2020

Published 7 July 2020

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3934860

Keywords: social protection, gender equality, women, reform, law, law, decision, state, society, family, rehabilitation, domestic violence, oppression, violence, political law, elections, constitution, party, country, spirituality, ethics, strategy,

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Today, Uzbekistan is rapidly developing at a new stage of development. The new image of our country is being formed as a result of ongoing reforms based on the wise traditions of our ancestors. In the works of our great ancestors Abu Nasra Farobi, Amir Temur, Alisher Navoi, Zakhiriddin Muhammad Babur, Abdullah Avloni, Abdurauf Fitrat, special attention is paid to the role of women in society and their social protection. In particular, Alisher Navoi in his works on the glorification of women, their strengthening in the family and society, said that "there are many women in the world who are famous for their intelligence, courage and wisdom, beauty, thoughtfulness and patience, kindness and devotion." emphasizes.

Our people will always respect Tomaris, Bibikhanum, Gulbadanbegim, Zebunniso, Nodira, Uvaysy, Anbar Otin, Zulfiya and hundreds of other women who have left an indelible mark on the great history of our state with their courage and perseverance, intelligence, elegance and delicacy. Ensuring that their unique spiritual and moral qualities are preserved in the image of the women of our country to show our youth the life and work of great women who have made a worthy contribution to the treasury of world culture, prevent negative situations, find ways to solve problems existing in society is important condition that they live contented and happy.

Women are active members of society, which ensure the stability of the spiritual environment in the country and in the family. Currently, on the basis of the Strategy of Action of the Republic of Uzbekistan in five priority areas for the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021, a wide range of measures are being taken to protect women, increase their socio-political activity, support motherhood and childhood, and strengthen the family. comprehensive work in progress¹. Social protection is a measure taken by the state to maintain a decent standard of living for all citizens while achieving social equality.²

A woman of Uzbekistan seeks to preserve the social and spiritual environment in the family with her positive qualities, to be an example for society, each member of the family with her moral, spiritual and moral qualities. Regulates relationships between family members with unique female skills. He always appears as a symbol of kindness, which gives a positive mood to others. The Jadid thinker Fitrat wrote in his book "Family": "The fate of a nation depends on the condition of the family in which it lives...."³ She can cope with any problem in the family, at work, in society with the help of intelligence, behavioral culture, the subtle and mysterious aspects of female diplomacy, and with her broad horizons, knowledge, entrepreneurship, initiative and planning, she can be a good mentor and assistant to her husband. All this makes it necessary to ensure gender equality for women in the country.

Full and genuine equality between men and women is a vital element in a just and democratic society based on the rule of law. The holistic development of society and the improvement of the well-being of all its members require equal opportunities for the full and equal participation of men and women. The full and equal enjoyment of human rights by women is of paramount importance for the consolidation of peace and democracy in the country.

Especially in the current era of globalization, the protection of women's rights, freedoms and legitimate interests is becoming increasingly important. Increasing the socio-economic and political-legal activity of women is becoming a requirement of the time. Currently, about 50% of

¹Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 4947 "On the Strategy of actions for further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan". February 7, 2017.

² Sodiqova Sh. A country where the elderly are valued.-T.: New Century Generation, 2015.-175 –p.

³ Abdurauf Fitrat. Family.-T.: Spirituality, 1998, p.

the population of our country are women. The effective work of women in all areas, especially raising children, excellent services in family life cannot be appreciated by anything.

Analyzing international experience, a number of documents of the Organization for Security and Cooperation in Europe (Madrid-1983, Vienna-1989, Moscow-1991, Istanbul-1999, Maastricht-2003, Sofia-2004, Ljubljana-2005, Athens-2009) promote equality among women, increasing the role of women at all levels of decision-making, creating opportunities for women to participate in political and social life, taking concrete measures to achieve the goals of gender equality in all legislative, judicial and executive branches of government, in elected government posts, to promote equal participation of women and men in political parties in order to achieve gender balance and achieve not only legal, but also practical equality between men and women.

Recognizing the supremacy of universally recognized norms of international law, over the past period, our country has undertaken a series of reforms to ensure equal rights and opportunities for women and men. In particular, article 46 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan enshrines the equal rights of women and men. On May 6, 1995, our country adopted the Declaration on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women, adopted on December 18, 1979 in New York, August 30, 1997, on the political rights of women, on equal incentives for men and women for equal work. conventions have been added.

Over the past two years, more than 15 legal acts on the radical improvement of the status of women have been signed and implemented in accordance with the requirements of international standards. In particular, on September 2, 2019, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 562 "On Guarantees of Equal Rights and Opportunities for Women and Men" and No. 561 "On the Protection of Women from Oppression and Violence" were adopted.

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 5325 of February 2, 2018 "On measures to radically improve activities in the field of supporting women and strengthening the family" of July 2, 2018 "On social rehabilitation and adaptation, as well as the prevention of domestic violence". Decree No. PQ-3827 of March 7, 2019 "On measures to improve the employment system" and No. PP-4235 "On measures to further strengthen women's labor rights guarantees and support entrepreneurship".

One of the recommendations made by the Committee on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women on the basis of the fifth periodic report of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the implementation of the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women is the adoption of a law guaranteeing equality between men and women.

In accordance with the Convention, States parties, in the context of their efforts to eliminate discrimination against women:

- incorporate the principle of equality of men and women in the legal system of the country, repeal all laws that are discriminatory against women, and adopt appropriate laws prohibiting any discrimination against women;
- take all appropriate measures, including measures to improve legislation, in all areas, in particular in the political, social, economic and cultural spheres, to ensure the full active participation of women and the realization of their potential;
- adoption of temporary special measures to accelerate the actual (actual) equality of women;
- undertake to take measures to eliminate social norms and attitudes that give preference to one sex over the other in society.

The Law on Guarantees of Equal Rights and Opportunities for Women and Men stipulates that the state shall ensure equal rights for women and men in the exercise of

personal, political, economic, social and cultural rights, as well as in the management of society and public affairs. guarantees equal participation in the electoral process.

In the elections of the presiding civil assemblies in the country in May 2019, 1,025 women were elected chairmen of self-government bodies, while the proportion of women in various enterprises increased from 44.2 percent in 2017 to 45.3 percent in 2019.

Today, one of the deputy leaders in almost all parties is a woman who has female wings.

About 300 NGOs deal with women's issues. In February 2019, the Republican Women's Forum "Experience of Non-Governmental Organizations in Enhancing the Social and Political Activity of Women" was held in February 2019 to coordinate the activities of NGOs and exchange experience between them. An NGO club has been created.

The knowledge and wide use of these opportunities contributed not only to the democratic conduct of elections, but also to the development of civil society in our country.

Such cooperation will further develop the potential of women in our country, strengthen their leadership skills, manifest themselves as politicians, leaders and public figures, as well as expand their participation in ongoing socio-political, economic, informational and ideological reforms in our country.

The 1952 Convention on the Political Rights of Women provides that women have the right to vote in any election on an equal basis with men without any discrimination. In the OSCE Copenhagen Document, all people are equal before the law and have the same right to equal protection under the law without any discrimination. In this regard, the law prohibits any discrimination and guarantees equal and effective protection of all persons from discrimination of any quality.

Women can participate in the election process as equal and free, open and transparent, like men, as voters, candidates, members of election commissions, observers, authorized representatives of the party, and proxies.

"Guarantees of equal rights and opportunities for women and men in the exercise of suffrage" are enshrined in a separate chapter of the Law "On Guarantees of Equal Rights and Opportunities for Women and Men".

According to her, women and men have equal rights to elect and be elected to representative bodies of power.

Political parties provide equal rights and opportunities for women and men when nominating candidates for deputies of the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan and local councils of people's deputies.

Equal rights and opportunities for women and men were ensured during the formation of the Central Election Commission of the Republic of Uzbekistan, regional, district, city, district and district election commissions for elections and referenda.

The number of female voters in our country exceeds 10 million. Given that this is a very important and significant indicator, in 2019 the Central Election Commission and the Women's Committee of Uzbekistan signed an agreement on cooperation in the preparation and conduct of elections to the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis, regional, district and city councils. The agreement establishes specific measures to improve the legal culture of women, girls who vote for the first time to ensure their active participation in elections and voting. A third of the Central Election Commission, in other words, seven members, are women.

According to articles 70.91 of the Electoral Code, the number of women should be at least thirty percent of the total number of candidates nominated by a political party. Setting the norm for increasing the number of women candidates is a global practice, as evidenced by the

laws of Albania, Bosnia, Herzegovina, Macedonia, Greece, Montenegro, Poland, San Marino, Serbia, Slovenia, Armenia, Kyrgyzstan and Spain.

Voluntary or mandatory quotas for women candidates have been registered in France, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey and the UK.

Of the new candidates to the Legislative Chamber in the 2019 elections, 440 men (58.7%) and 310 women (41.3%). This is almost 10 percent (31.8) more than in the parliamentary elections in December 2014. The largest number of women came from the People's Democratic Party (48%), followed by the Social Democratic Justice Party (43.3%), followed by the Movement of Entrepreneurs and Entrepreneurs - Liberal Democratic Party of Uzbekistan (42.7%), Democratic party of national revival (36.7%), Ecological Party (36%). As we see, the number of women made up more than thirty percent of the total number of candidates nominated by political parties.

Although our laws provide for a 30 percent quota for women in parliamentary elections, this was not the case in practice. Last year, for the first time in the history of our country, the number of women in the national parliament has grown to today's level. Of the 150 deputies elected to the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis, 48 or 32% were women. In the Senate, this figure was about 25 percent.

Women also make up 31 percent of local council members. As a result, the Uzbek parliament rose to 37th place among 190 national parliaments in the world in the number of women deputies. However, 5 years ago he was in 128th place. Such dramatic positive changes mean that the parliamentary elections not only took place, but the slogan "New Uzbekistan - new elections" directly reflected on life. In the end, when women make decisions in the field of social issues, first of all, these problems - the pain of people, like the problem of people, are inextricably linked with the problems that they face day and night.

Secondly, the reason why a woman understands social issues more deeply is that she, as a housewife, child educator, psychiatrist who cares about her health, and also an active politician in life, seeks to make laws more vital by expressing specific problems solving problems.

Consequently, the sharp increase in the number of women in parliament and the appointment of six women as governors of the districts played an important role in ensuring gender equality in our country. The Senate of the Oliy Majlis, in addition to providing full support to women leaders, works closely with them in the development and implementation of regional development programs.

The decision of the senators to appoint Feruza Yuldashevna Makhmudova Ambassador Extraordinary and Plenipotentiary of the Republic of Uzbekistan to Israel on June 19, 2020 at the 5th plenary meeting of the Senate of the Oliy Majlis is a testament to the growing attention to women and gender equality in our country. Feruza Yuldashevna is the only woman among the ambassadors of more than 130 countries of independent Uzbekistan. The beginning of this process will pave the way for the further expansion of our female ambassadors.

It also opened up wide opportunities for women to directly participate in the implementation of decisions affecting the fate of the state and society, in particular, in the development, adoption and implementation of laws and reforms. The fact that women senators and deputies together with our local officials deeply realize this responsibility, study problems and make an important contribution to their solution is directly related to the issue of gender equality.

Thus, it is important for society and the state that women with political maturity, industriousness and intellect demonstrate their potential in elections, increase the number of

women elected to parliament and local councils, and take into account the interests and views of women in the legislative process and the state budget. allows to take into account issues of gender equality in the formation. The elections of women deputies serve to strengthen legislative and parliamentary oversight to strengthen the family, protect motherhood and childhood, ensure the rights and freedoms of women, legitimate interests and increase the participation of women in social, economic, political, legal and cultural life.

Despite the fact that women have equal rights, our laws do not have any restrictions or, even if they are eliminated, they are not enough to ensure gender tension. Analyzing world experience, the reputable World Economic Forum annually prepares a report on gender differences in society (between men and women). This report takes into account differences in the roles of women and men in political life, economics, secondary education and access to health services. If we look at the indicators of 149 countries in 2018 (Uzbekistan is not included in this report), we will see that the biggest difference is in political life, followed by the economy, and the smallest difference is in secondary education and health. The region with the best results in this regard is Western Europe, followed by North America. In general, most of the countries that achieve high results in ensuring gender equality are economically developed or rapidly developing countries.

It is estimated that Western Europe, considered the most advanced country in terms of gender equality, will achieve full gender equality in about 60 years at the current pace, while other regions of the world will need several times to achieve this result. This means that it is not enough to establish equal rights in the legislation, an active policy is required. Equal participation of men and women in society is an important factor in the development of the country, since the emergence of a highly competitive environment in the country allows this country to fully utilize its potential.

It is also important to take effective measures for the equal participation of men and women in politics, economics and society and pursue an active policy that will lead to significant positive results.

Earlier, the concept of gender equality was practically not mentioned in the socio-political, socio-economic life of our country. That is why misconceptions about gender equality have formed in the minds of our people. Presumably, the term "gender equality" was adopted to mean that women are superior to men, that they are ignored, that men have the right to vote. However, gender equality means giving men and women equal opportunities in everything. That is, the creation of equal opportunities for men and women in the field of education, career choice, promotion is the essence of the concept of gender equality or gender equality - equal opportunities for women and men to exercise their rights in economic, social, cultural and political development. The distribution of jobs by gender is that there is no distribution of men and women in the economy, which is why men or women predominate in other sectors of the economy. Gender equality is equal representation of men and women at all levels of socio-economic, political, cultural, scientific and educational life of a society. Gender roles, on the other hand, represent social roles assigned to men and women in accordance with social and cultural norms that exist in society and in a particular historical situation.

The work done in our country on this issue gives significant positive results. In particular, the Committee on Women and Gender Equality was created in the Senate of the Oliy Majlis. A separate commission on gender equality has been created, which annually submits to the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan a report on the state of affairs in the field of equal rights and opportunities for women and men. The Gender Equality Commission is composed of many non-governmental organizations, active women and men, and world experience is being

studied in collaboration. At the same time, both norms of the current legislation are analyzed by both structures from the point of view of equality between women and men, and the legislation is being improved on the basis of scientifically based conclusions.

Now an official has been appointed to ensure equal rights and opportunities for women and men in state bodies. The fulfillment of the duties of an authorized person is entrusted to one of the deputy heads of the state body.

A new institution called the gender-legal examination of regulatory documents and their projects has become part of the law. A proposal was developed to create advisory councils on gender equality issues in each working group, which is reflected in the relevant legal documents. The members of the council are up to seven employees of the enterprise, which is headed by the deputy head of the same team responsible for social issues. The main task of the Council will be to ensure equal opportunities for women and men in all departments and territorial structures from top to bottom. Systematically analyzes and draws conclusions on issues such as salary setting, equal treatment of women and men in recommended positions, including women candidates on a reserve personnel base in each enterprise and organization, and their preparation for leadership positions. At the same time, he is also studying the conditions created for women in the field.

This means that relations between women and men in society are determined primarily by the characteristics of the national culture and are improved in accordance with changes in society and living conditions. In our country, women and men also have a place and place in public life. Opportunities for women to realize their talents and abilities, in addition to improving gender relations, also affect the preservation of a woman's national identity, such as respect, respect and attention to her.

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Cite this article:

Author(s), NARBAEVA TANZILA KAMALOVNA, (2020). “Legal Basis of Social Protection of Women and Gender Equality”. Name of the Journal: International Journal of Academic Research in Business, Arts and Science, (IJARBAS.COM), P, 1- 9. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3934860> , Issue: 7, Vol.: 2, Article: 1, Month: June, Year: 2020. Retrieved from <https://www.ijarbas.com/all-issues/>

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